

Coach–Athlete Communication in Elite Badminton: Exploring Interpersonal Dynamics in an Indonesian High-Performance Training Environment at Djarum Badminton Club

Debora Pungky Cahyadewi¹, Tomoliyus², Endang Rini Sukamti³, Abdul Alim⁴

^{1,2,3,4}Department of Sport Coaching Education, Faculty of Sport Sciences and Health, Yogyakarta State University, Indonesia

ABSTRACT: Coach–athlete communication plays a crucial role in shaping training effectiveness and athlete performance, particularly in elite sport environments. This study aims to explore the interpersonal dynamics of coach–athlete communication in elite badminton within an Indonesian high-performance training context at Djarum Badminton Club. A qualitative approach was employed using semi-structured interviews and non-participant observations involving coaches and athletes. Data were analyzed through thematic analysis to identify key patterns in communication practice. The findings reveal that coach–athlete communication is multidimensional, encompassing instructional, interpersonal, and psychological functions. Communication serves not only as a medium for delivering technical instructions but also as a mechanism for building relationships, regulating motivation, and supporting athletes' psychological readiness. Effective communication is characterized by adaptability, combining verbal and non-verbal strategies, and responsiveness to individual athlete needs. However, communication barriers were identified, including differences in language, communication styles, and hierarchical relationships influenced by cultural context. This study contributes to the literature by integrating multiple dimensions of communication within a single analytical framework and by providing empirical evidence from an underrepresented context in sport communication research. Practically, the findings highlight the importance of adaptive and culturally sensitive communication competencies for coaches in elite training environments. Future research is recommended to examine diverse sports and cultural settings and to incorporate quantitative approaches for broader generalization.

KEYWORDS: coach-athlete communication, elite badminton, interpersonal communication, sport coaching, qualitative research

I. INTRODUCTION

In competitive sports, success is determined not only by physical ability and technique, but also by various factors, one of which is the quality of social interactions that develop during the training process (Dunne et al., 2022). Interactions during the training process are primarily mediated through communication between coaches and athletes, which influences performance and warrants attention as it plays a role in conveying instructions, building shared understanding, and shaping athletes' attitudes and behaviors during training (Zubić, 2024). In the context of sports, communication serves not only as a means of conveying messages but is also used to facilitate interpersonal relationships; active interpersonal communication can strengthen interpersonal bonds (Sofia et al., 2020; Zis et al., 2021).

Several studies indicate that coach-athlete communication significantly contributes to athletes' performance and the quality of the coach-athlete relationship during training (Nicholls & Perry, 2020). Effective communication enhances athletes' understanding of the training program and strengthens their trust and engagement in the training process (Dunne et al., 2022). This is reflected in training practices where coaches support athletes during the training process and assist them during competitions. Conversely, ineffective communication can lead to misunderstandings, interpersonal conflicts, and a decline in athlete performance (Karafil & Ulaş, 2024). Additionally, interpersonal communication plays a role in shaping athletes' psychological experiences, including motivation, self-confidence, and engagement in training. (Hampson & Jowett, 2021). In the context of elite sports, the coach-athlete relationship formed through communication is a key factor in supporting the success of athlete development (Nicholls & Perry, 2020; Haryanto et al., 2024).

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Although research on communication in sports has expanded, studies specifically examining coach–athlete communication dynamics in badminton, particularly in the context of elite training, remain limited. However, the nature of badminton as an individual sport with a high intensity of coach–athlete interaction allows for the formation of communication patterns that differ from those in other sports. Communication patterns between coaches and athletes can also be influenced by differences in social and cultural contexts, as well as training systems (Hampson & Jowett, 2021). The limitations of this research result in a lack of understanding regarding how coach–athlete communication plays a role in supporting the effectiveness of the training process and optimizing athlete development. Furthermore, most research on coach-athlete communication patterns has been conducted in Western contexts, so there has been limited exploration of how social and cultural factors within development systems in Asia—particularly in Indonesia—influence these dynamics.

As one of Indonesia’s elite badminton clubs, PB Djarum has a structured and sustainable athlete development system and has produced high-performing athletes at both the national and international levels (Pratama & Nurrachmad, 2025). The competitive training environment and the intensity of interaction between coaches and athletes make this context relevant for a deeper examination of communication patterns (Karafil & Ulaş, 2024). Additionally, as a boarding-school-based club, the athletes being developed come from various regions across Indonesia. Consequently, athletes possess diverse communication styles due to their varying social and cultural backgrounds. In this context, communication is not merely about conveying technical instructions but also shapes the quality of the coach-athlete relationship, which significantly influences the effectiveness of the training process (Nicholls & Perry, 2020).

Based on this, this study aims to examine the dynamics of coach-athlete communication in elite badminton training at PB Djarum. Unlike previous studies, which tended to examine communication in isolation or focused on team sports contexts in Western countries, this study presents empirical evidence from the context of elite badminton training in Asia as a representation of non-Western high-performance training environments, particularly in Indonesia. This study focuses on how interpersonal communication is formed, how messages are conveyed and understood, and the factors that influence the effectiveness of communication in training. This study employs a qualitative approach and is expected to contribute to and expand the field of sports communication research, as well as provide a contextual perspective on communication dynamics within elite athlete development systems, particularly in the sport of badminton.

II. METHODS

This study employs a qualitative approach to understand the dynamics of coach-athlete communication in the context of elite badminton coaching. This approach was chosen because it allows for an in-depth exploration of the experiences, meanings, and social interactions that occur during the training process (Creswell & Poth, 2020). This approach is relevant in the context of sports, where coach-athlete communication is a dynamic and contextual social process, thus requiring a deep understanding of the participants’ experiences (Dunne et al., 2022).

A. *Participants & Research Site*

This study was conducted within the PB Djarum training environment, specifically at the Djarum Jati Badminton Hall and the Djarum Kaliputu Badminton Hall in Kudus. The study was carried out in March 2023. Research participants were selected using purposive sampling, which involves selecting informants based on specific criteria relevant to the research objectives (Palinkas et al., 2020). The participant composition was considered sufficient to achieve data saturation and provide in-depth contextual insights into coach-athlete communication dynamics. The participants in this study consisted of one person serving as the Executive Chairman of PB Djarum, two coaches, and seven athletes who had been training for more than one year and had experience at the national and international levels. This composition of participants was chosen to obtain a comprehensive perspective on the dynamics of communication from various roles within the development system.

B. *Data Collection Methods*

Data for this study were collected through in-depth interviews and observation. In-depth interviews were conducted to explore participants’ experiences, perceptions, and interpretations of the communication that occurred during the training process. Interviews were conducted in person with coaches and athletes to obtain in-depth and contextual primary data. In-depth interviews lasted 20–30 minutes per participant, focusing on exploring communication experiences within the training context. This method allows researchers to understand how messages are conveyed, received, and interpreted by participants (Kallio et al., 2020). Data collection was conducted until data saturation was reached, at which point no significant new information was found.

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The observation involved directly observing the interactions between coaches and athletes during training sessions, including how coaches conveyed instructions, provided motivation, and built interpersonal relationships with athletes. The observation took place over six days and covered several training sessions, both in singles and doubles categories, allowing the researcher to observe variations in communicative interactions across different training contexts. This observation aimed to provide a realistic picture of communication practices in a natural context (Angrosino, 2021).

C. Data Collection Technique

Data analysis was conducted using thematic analysis to identify communication patterns emerging in coach-athlete interactions, following a six-step process: (1) familiarization with the data through repeated reading of interview transcripts and observation notes, (2) systematic initial coding of relevant units of meaning, (3) grouping codes into preliminary themes, (4) reviewing and verifying the alignment of themes with the data, (5) defining and naming themes conceptually, and (6) compiling a narrative report of the analysis results (Braun & Clarke, 2006). The analysis is conducted iteratively by comparing data from interviews and observations to produce a deep and consistent interpretation. This process allows researchers to identify recurring communication patterns and the meanings constructed in coach-athlete interactions.

D. Data Validity

Data validity in this study was assessed using triangulation and member checking to enhance data credibility. Triangulation was conducted by comparing data from various sources (coaches and athletes) and various methods (interviews and observations) to enhance the validity of the findings (Nowell et al., 2021). Additionally, member checking was conducted by confirming the results of the interpretation with the participants to ensure consistency between the data obtained and their actual experiences (Creswell & Poth, 2018). This approach aims to ensure that the research results possess a high level of trustworthiness and are scientifically accountable (Nowell et al., 2017).

III. RESULT

Based on the results of interviews and observations, this study identified five main themes that describe the dynamics of communication between coaches and athletes in elite badminton training at Djarum Badminton Club, namely: (1) communication as the delivery of technical instructions, (2) communication in building interpersonal relationships, (3) communication as a means of motivation, (4) barriers to communication, and (5) adaptation of coaching styles.

The findings indicate that coach-athlete communication plays a key role in conveying technical instructions during the training process. Coaches provide direct and repeated guidance tailored to the athletes' level of understanding. This is evident in the coach's statement: "Some athletes do not grasp explanations quickly... so it is necessary to repeat explanations so that they can understand and put them into practice" (Coach 1). In addition, athletes also emphasized the importance of clarity in the delivery of instructions: "I understand better when the coach demonstrates directly; that way, I grasp the movement or direction of the strike more clearly" (Athlete 1). These findings indicate that the effectiveness of communication is significantly influenced by the method of delivering instructions as well as the coach's ability to adapt communication methods to the athletes' needs.

Communication also helps build interpersonal relationships between coaches and athletes. A good relationship is characterized by open communication and personal interaction. A coach stated: "To understand an athlete's character, I engage in one-on-one conversations... not only that, but I also seek information from their friends" (Coach 1). Athletes also feel that communication brings them closer to their coaches: "Through communication, I can get closer to my coach and teammates" (Athlete 6). However, this closeness is not always consistent across all athletes. Some athletes still face barriers to openness: "Sometimes I'm not brave enough because I feel shy around the coach" (Athlete 3). These findings indicate that interpersonal communication is a key factor in building relationships, yet it is influenced by the athletes' personalities and courage.

Communication also serves as a means of providing motivation and psychological support. Coaches use communication to boost morale and guide athletes' attitudes. A coach stated: "There are also athletes who need to be 'warmed up every day' by being constantly motivated" (Coach 1). From the athletes' perspective, the coach's experience is also a source of motivation: "The coach's experience is important and influential for me... so that we know how to deal with problems" (Athlete 1). These findings indicate that communication has an important role in the psychological aspects of athletes, not only influencing motivation but also shaping their mental readiness to face the pressures of training and competition.

Although communication plays a vital role, there are several barriers in the communication process. These barriers include differences in language, understanding, and the manner in which messages are conveyed. One athlete stated: "The coach gave instructions in Javanese... I just stayed silent because I didn't understand" (Athlete 2). Additionally, barriers also arise from the coach speaking too quickly: "Sometimes I don't quite understand because the coach speaks too fast" (Athlete 3). These findings

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indicate that the effectiveness of communication is influenced by language compatibility, speaking pace, and similarity of understanding; thus, non-adaptive communication has the potential to lead to miscommunication.

The findings indicate that coaches adjust their communication style based on athletes' characteristics, as each athlete has a different way of understanding. A coach stated: "Some athletes understand immediately, while others need detailed explanations" (Coach 2). Additionally, cultural factors also influence communication: "Athletes from different regions have different ways of communicating... so adjustments are necessary" (Coach 2). These findings indicate that communication in sports coaching is situational and flexible and requires adaptability from coaches, thus making a coach's communication competence one of the key factors in the success of the training process.

IV. DISCUSSION

Coach-athlete communication in elite badminton training is multidimensional, encompassing instructional, interpersonal, and psychological functions. These findings confirm that communication serves not only as a medium for conveying messages but also as a technique for integrating technical, relational, and psychological aspects into the elite athlete development process. Thus, communication can be understood as a key element that mediates the overall effectiveness of training.

A. Communication as a Means of Conveying Instructions

Findings indicate that instructional communication is adaptive and iterative, particularly in adjusting to athletes' levels of understanding. This aligns with the concept of instructional communication in sports, which emphasizes the importance of message clarity and flexibility in communication methods during the training process (Hampson & Jowett, 2021). Similar findings also indicate that interactive and contextual communication can enhance athletes' technical understanding (Dunne et al., 2022).

Evidence from this study shows that the effectiveness of communication depends not only on the clarity of instructions, but also on the instructor's ability to combine verbal and nonverbal communication, such as movement demonstrations. These findings reinforce the concept of scaffolding communication in motor learning (Light & Harvey, 2020), in which repetition and demonstration are key strategies for improving skill comprehension.

These findings suggest that instructional communication in the training of elite athletes is not linear (from coach to athlete), but rather interactive and responsive to the individual needs of the athlete. This indicates that instructional communication functions as a process of negotiating meaning, rather than merely a transfer of information, and thus plays a crucial role in enhancing the effectiveness of technical learning.

B. Communication and the Development of the Coach-Athlete Relationship

Research findings indicate that interpersonal communication serves as the primary foundation for building the coach-athlete relationship. These findings align with the coach-athlete relationship model (3+1Cs Model) developed by Sophie Jowett, which emphasizes the importance of closeness, commitment, and complementarity in the coach-athlete relationship (Jowett, 2017; Jowett & Shanmugam, 2021).

These research findings can be understood through the lens of relational coaching (Jowett & Shanmugam, 2016), which emphasizes that the coach-athlete relationship is not only built through interaction but also as a dynamic process of fostering emotional connection and role alignment between the coach and the athlete (complementarity). In this approach, interpersonal communication, such as one-on-one interactions, reflects the relational coaching perspective and serves as a crucial means of fostering emotional closeness (Jowett & Shanmugam, 2016).

Research by Nicholls & Perry (2020) also indicates that open interpersonal communication contributes to the quality of relationships and athlete satisfaction. Interestingly, however, the findings of this study reveal barriers, such as shyness and hierarchy, suggesting that the quality of relationships is determined not only by the frequency of communication but also by the extent to which such communication fosters psychological safety for athletes.

These findings add a new dimension: the existence of barriers to openness due to hierarchical and cultural factors. This expands the concept of relational coaching by demonstrating that the relational context in sports can be influenced by social and cultural contexts. Thus, this study contributes by showing that the coach-athlete relationship model must be understood contextually, particularly within social and cultural contexts characterized by strong hierarchical values.

C. Communication as a Mechanism for Regulating Motivation and Providing Psychological Support

The findings indicate that communication serves as a mechanism for regulating motivation and providing psychological support. This aligns with Self-Determination Theory (SDT), which emphasizes that social support and positive communication can play a crucial role in fulfilling three basic psychological needs: autonomy, competence, and relatedness (Deci & Ryan, 2020);

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Ryan & Deci, 2020). The fulfillment of these three needs is key to enhancing individuals' intrinsic motivation and psychological well-being.

In this study, the coach's supportive communication and personalized approach reflect efforts to meet these psychological needs, particularly relatedness and competence. This indicates that communication not only plays a role in enhancing technical understanding and emotional connection but also serves as a means to build athletes' self-confidence and mental readiness. These findings are consistent with the research by Lafrenière et al. (2020), which shows that autonomy-supportive coaching contributes positively to athletes' intrinsic motivation and psychological well-being. Furthermore, supportive and empathetic communication can enhance athletes' self-confidence and mental resilience in coping with competitive pressure (Olympiou et al., 2008). This study is also consistent with the motivational climate framework proposed by Joan L. Duda (2013), which states that the social environment shaped by coaches through communication can create a task-oriented climate or an ego-oriented climate. Positive and constructive communication tends to foster a climate that supports development, thereby enhancing athletes' long-term motivation (Appleton & Duda, 2016).

This study on the development of elite athletes at PB Djarum, this understanding is expanded by demonstrating that coaches not only serve as technical instructors on the field but also play a role in maintaining motivational stability and addressing athletes' psychological needs, particularly when facing the pressures of training and competition. Thus, communication can be understood as an active mechanism in maintaining athletes' motivational stability and performance.

D. Communication Barriers in Social and Cultural Contexts

This study shows that communication barriers can be influenced by linguistic, cultural, and social structural factors. These findings align with those of Karafil and Ulaş (2024), who state that miscommunication in sports often occurs due to differences in perception and communication styles.

The use of regional languages, such as Javanese, indicates that communication barriers are not only related to language but also to cultural meaning systems. This reinforces the perspective of intercultural communication, which emphasizes the importance of meaning alignment in cross-cultural interactions (Blodgett et al., 2014; Schinke et al., 2020). Furthermore, these findings can also be explained through the concept of power distance (Hofstede, 2011), where hierarchical relationships can limit athletes' openness in communicating with coaches. Thus, communication barriers in this context are not merely individual in nature but reflect the social and cultural structures within the training environment.

These findings imply that the effectiveness of communication between coaches and athletes is determined not only by the clarity of the message but also by the ability to understand the culture and adapt language and social structures within the training environment.

E. Adapting Communication Styles as a Coaching Competency

Findings indicate that coaches actively adapt their communication styles based on athletes' characteristics, such as their level of understanding, responsiveness, and individual backgrounds. This aligns with the concept of transformational leadership in sports, which emphasizes the importance of flexibility and adaptability in leadership to enhance coaching effectiveness (Bass & Riggio, 2006). Research by Davis, Jowett, and Tafvelin (2019) as well as Downham & Cushion (2020) confirms that modern coaches are required to possess adaptive and contextual interpersonal communication competencies, and emphasizes that communication flexibility is a crucial component of effective coaching leadership. However, this study indicates that communicative adaptation serves not only to enhance understanding but also as a strategy to overcome communication barriers arising from cultural differences and social structures. Thus, the ability to adapt communication is not merely an additional skill but a strategic competency that determines coaching effectiveness and plays a role in optimizing the training process.

V. CONCLUSIONS

This study demonstrates that coach–athlete communication in elite badminton training is a multidimensional process that encompasses instructional, interpersonal, and psychological functions. Communication serves not only as a means of conveying instructions but also as a primary mechanism for building relationships, regulating motivation, and supporting athletes' mental readiness to face various performance demands.

The findings confirm that the effectiveness of communication is determined by the coach's ability to adapt their communication style to the athlete's characteristics and to integrate verbal and nonverbal communication into the training process. Furthermore, interpersonal communication has proven to be the foundation for building a high-quality coach–athlete relationship, although in practice it is influenced by social and cultural dynamics, such as hierarchy and the use of local languages. This study also indicates

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that communication in the development of elite athletes plays a strategic role as a mechanism for regulating motivation and performance stability. In this regard, supportive communication not only enhances athletes' understanding and self-confidence but also contributes to psychological resilience in coping with the pressures of training and competition.

This research contributes theoretically by expanding the field of sports communication research through the integration of instructional, relational, and psychological dimensions within a single analytical framework. Contextually, this study offers a perspective on the elite badminton development system in Asia, particularly in Indonesia, which remains underrepresented in the international literature. Practically, these findings underscore the importance of developing coaches' communication competencies, particularly regarding adaptability, cultural sensitivity, and interpersonal approaches within diverse training environments.

Thus, coach-athlete communication can no longer be viewed as a supporting aspect but rather as a primary determinant of success in elite sports development. However, this study has limitations regarding its geographical scope and the number of participants, so the results cannot yet be widely generalized. Therefore, future research is recommended to examine coach–athlete communication across various sports and different cultural contexts, as well as to integrate quantitative approaches to test the relationships between variables more comprehensively. This is important to strengthen the validity of the findings while expanding the contribution of communication studies in elite sports.

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